

Photonic and Quantum Communication Technologies for Optical Networks Evolution

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ABSTRACT

The role of photonic technologies and optical communications, as well as quantum communications, is particularly relevant to address the societal challenges posed by 6G networks and for a sustainable network evolution. This work focuses on recent advances in programmable multi-dimensional (spectrally and spatially multiplexed) transmission systems and adaptive high-capacity (multi-Tb/s) photonic transceivers to address a sustainable capacity scaling and the needs of future optical networks. It presents our approach and proposed solutions, and discusses how to enable high-performance, flexibility, agility, cost/power efficiency and security, promoting an optimal resource usage. To address security aspects, quantum key distribution (QKD) technology is considered in coexistence with classical/conventional systems.

Keywords: Sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver (S-BVT), programmable (SDN-enabled) multidimensional transmission, future optical networks, quantum key distribution (QKD).

1. INTRODUCTION

To meet the future traffic demand, coping with the continuous increase of the capacity and dynamicity of beyond 5G and 6G networks, it is required to investigate novel photonic solutions enabling multi-Tb/s transmission with high flexibility, adaptability and scalability. Also, exploring multiple bands beyond the C-band and multiple dimensions including the spatial one is a recent trend towards targeting this goal [1, 2]. In this context, the disaggregation paradigm is promoted by operators in view of reducing the network cost, enabling interoperability and resource sharing for a sustainable network evolution.

The available multi-dimensional resources/infrastructure sharing, and the promotion of open and disaggregated paradigms, make privacy a critical concern to deal with. Furthermore, the recent advances on quantum computing represents a threat for secure communications and the network security appears a critical issue to be urgently addressed from the scientific community. Thus, in addition to flexible, scalable and high-capacity connectivity solutions, another important aspect to take into account in future networks is to enable quantum secure communications. Accordingly, in view of a sustainable optical network evolution, the coexistence of quantum communications with classical optical communications and their integration within the network infrastructure should be carefully addressed.

In this work, we present our approach and proposed solutions, reporting recent results, to meet the need of future optical networks and our vision towards their future evolution.

2. PROGRAMMABLE MULTIDIMENSIONAL TRANSMISSION AND PHOTONIC TRANSCEIVERS

To guarantee a sustainable capacity scaling in future optical networks, a suitable combination of wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) and space division multiplexing (SDM) transmission is needed to fully exploit the spectral and spatial dimensions. In addition to the adoption of the flexi-grid paradigm by assigning fine granularity channel slots of 12.5 GHz, or even finer [3], an extension of the optical spectrum used by WDM to the entire set of available bands (L, C, S, O and E) is envisioned to fully exploit the frequency dimension [1]. This allows increasing the optical bandwidth by a factor of 10 and reuse the already deployed standard single mode fibers (SSMFs). However, an upgrade of the network elements, comprising transceivers, amplifiers, filters and nodes (reconfigurable optical add/drop multiplexers, ROADMs), is required to enable the use of multiple bands beyond the C-band. Regarding the spatial dimension, different approaches can be envisioned, including the transmission through bundles of SSMFs or other specialty fibers, such as multicore fibers (MCF), multimode fibers (MMF), or few-mode multicore fibers (FM-MCFs), to provide further scaling towards multi-Tb/s capacities. Thus, the adoption of multidimensional transmission is key in future optical networks.

To efficiently using the available resources and infrastructure, a modular design can be envisioned for the transmission system, adopting a grow-as-needed approach. Operators can install and assign opportunely additional bands/resources adopting a pay-as-you-grow strategy. Accordingly, a suitable synergy of software defined networking (SDN) and photonic technologies is needed to target the required flexibility, programmability and interoperability, while reducing cost, power consumption and footprint of the envisioned

transmission solutions [2]. Hence, to enable future agile and high-capacity networks, programmable and modular photonic transceiver architectures should be carefully designed.

2.1 Modular and programmable S-BVT

Modular and sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceivers (S-BVTs) allow an optimal network resources usage to enable future connectivity and scalability to multi-Tb/s capacity in a grow-as-needed fashion [4]. Programmable (SDN-enabled) S-BVTs have the ability of supporting flexible rate, adaptive reach, and connectivity to multiple endpoints simultaneously (slice-ability, multi-flow operation). The relevance of point-to-multipoint solutions have been recently highlighted by the industry for saving costs and enabling more agile paradigms [5].

Figure 1 illustrates the schematic of the modular and programmable S-BVT architecture that we propose. Adaptive digital signal processing (DSP) based on multicarrier technology (e.g., orthogonal frequency division multiplexing, OFDM) is considered to enable flexibility at the subwavelength granularity. This allows manipulating the spectral subcarrier contribution at the digital level, with optimal loading of each subcarrier. Alternative transmitter and receiver options have been explored to provide a suitable trade-off in terms of performance and cost/power efficiency according to the targeted application and network segment [2]. Direct modulation (DM) and direct detection (DD) are the most cost-effective options. Adopting both in the BVT implementation is an efficient solution for short-reach communications, while the performance is limited for covering metro-core multi-hop paths [4]. Thus, we propose to adopt external modulation combined with DD, and DM with the coherent receiver (CO-Rx) option, to achieve a good trade-off of performance and efficiency in terms of cost. In case of external modulation, performed with a simple Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM), a tunable laser source (TLS) allows to flexibly select the channel wavelength. For DM, the use of vertical cavity surface emitting lasers (VCSELs) is an attractive and efficient (in terms of cost and power consumption) BVT transmitter (BVTx) option. In fact, the availability of VCSEL technology (InP short-cavity) enables high modulation bandwidth (>18 GHz) and operation at long wavelengths [4]. The adoption of dense photonic integrated circuits (PICs) allows very compact and cost/power efficient designs, fostering component sharing and an improvement in the form-factor of pluggable optical interfaces [2]. Furthermore, with the advances in complementary metal oxide semiconductor technology, further power saving is possible, enabling advanced DSP (also exploiting multicarrier modulation) to enhance the transceiver performance, adaptability and flexibility [2]. As shown in Fig. 1, the S-BVT can be suitably configured and programmed by an SDN control plane, which enables to adapt the transmission according to the channel state information and traffic requirements over the established path.

Figure 1. S-BVT schematic with modular architecture and (SDN-enabled) programmability features. In the insets, alternative options for the transmitter and receiver front-end. The 4-node flexi-grid network of the ADRENALINE testbed, also including the 19-core MCF, is illustrated.

2.2 Multi-band and SDM S-BVT

The architecture in Figure 1 also includes the adoption of multiple bands: multi-band S-BVT. For example, the BVTs from 1 to $n-1$ (orange block) can work in the C-band (or even C+L), while the BVT array from n to N (yellow block) can operate in the S (or L) band. Further blocks can be included exploiting additional bands. Indeed, the transceiver elements should be specifically tailored/ designed to opportunely support the targeted bands. Similarly, the multi-flow aggregator/distributor, which can be implemented by means of a wavelength

selective switch (WSS), should support the wavelengths generated at the BVT blocks. It can be composed of multiple (WSS) blocks, each one working at the required band. Also, multiple flows can be generated to be multiplexed in the spatial dimension (SDM) and transmitted over a bundle of fibers or a MCF to further scale the S-BVT capacity.

In table 1, we report our recent experimental results within the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed, using alternative options for the BVT modules. The multi-hop paths over the ADRENALINE 4-node network (see Fig. 1) are established (spatial/spectral path and resource selection/allocation for the incoming connection request) by the SDN controller. It can eventually delegate the node configuration to a dedicated optical line system (OLS) controller (indicated with dashed line in Fig. 1). The SDM approach has been assessed adopting a 25km 19-core MCF. In the results reported in Table 1, OFDM signals of 20GHz (with external modulation) or 16GHz (with direct modulation) are considered, single sideband (SSB) and flexi-grid channels of 25GHz are taken into account. A VCSEL operating in the C-band with 10GHz bandwidth is adopted. This technology also offers solutions with higher bandwidth that can support 50Gb/s per flow (S-BVT slice) [4]. Interestingly, high speed InP VCSELs operating also in the L-band are available to eventually extend this S-BVT architecture to multi-band [6]. Multiple wavelengths in the L- and S-band have been enabled at the TLS and assessed in the ADRENALINE testbed achieving maximum capacities per slice >60Gb/s in back-to-back (B2B). A capacity of 21Gb/s is achieved with double sideband (DSB) transmission after 50km of SSMF without any filtering/amplification; with the C-band slice, 26Gb/s is obtained in the same conditions, while 50Gb/s can be obtained with SSB, filtering and amplifiers [7, 8].

The aggregated data rate can be increased to Tb/s by including/activating additional BVT elements/slices [9]. An aggregated capacity of 1.6 Tb/s of 25GHz spaced WDM/SDM (8x11) channels has been achieved with a VCSEL-based S-BVT over a 110km 5-hop metro network path, including 25Km 19-core MCF [10].

Table 1. S-BVT performance using different optoelectronic front-ends. RL indicates recirculating loop.

BVTx	BVRx	Capacity/channel (Gb/s)	Wavelength (nm)	MCF	Path	hop #	Ref.
MZM&TLS	DD	>60	1550.12, 1592.5, 1525	-	B2B	-	[7]
MZM&TLS	DD	50	1550.12	-	35 km	2	[11]
MZM&TLS	DD	50	1550.12	-	50 km	1	[8]
MZM&TLS (DSB)	DD	26	1550.12	-	50km (w/o filters/amp.)	1	[7]
MZM&TLS (DSB)	DD	21	1525, 1592.5	-	50km (w/o filters/amp.)	1	[7]
MZM&TLS	DD	35	1550.12	-	120km	3	[11]
MZM&TLS	DD	35	1550.12	8x25km	203km	RL	[9]
MZM&TLS	DD	24	1550.12	11x25km	279km	RL	[9]
VCSEL	DD	>30	1545.32	-	B2B	-	[4]
VCSEL	CO-Rx	>30	1545.32	-	B2B	-	[4]
VCSEL	CO-Rx	22	1545.32	25km	160km	6	[4]

3. QUANTUM SECURE COMMUNICATIONS

In the quantum era we are facing, reliable information security mechanisms are crucial, as well as their suitable integration in the current network infrastructure, for optimal resource usage and for a sustainable transition towards future quantum networks and the quantum Internet. In fact, as the security of current and future networks is threatened by the prospect of the quantum computing, it is particularly relevant to consider quantum technologies and quantum secure communications in preparation for the radical technological advance envisioned for future networks. Identifying and designing suitable cryptographic systems, taking into account the impact on the network infrastructure, are of paramount importance.

3.1 Quantum Key Distribution

QKD is one of the most promising technologies to ensure long-term security in optical networks.

Two major QKD flavours can be distinguished: the discrete variable (DV)-QKD and the continuous variable (CV)-QKD, trading-off longer reach against higher secure-key rate [12]. In the former, the adoption of single photon detectors is required, while the latter allows the adoption of optical coherent technologies and, thus, enables implementations more compatible with optical systems and facilitates its adoption and integration in optical networks. A coherent optical communication system operating in the quantum noise limit is ready for CV-QKD, and actual implementations adopting commercial off the shelf (COTS) components are possible, as recently demonstrated in [13]. In CV-QKD, Gaussian modulation (GM) and discrete modulation (DM) can be

adopted. DM protocols can outperform GM due to higher reconciliation efficiency and are more compatible with fiber optic communications equipment, further easing the integration in optical communication systems [12].

3.2 Coexistence and SDN aspects

The integration of quantum technologies in the current network infrastructure is a critical issue. The study and analysis of the coexistence of QKD and conventional systems is of special relevance for identifying optimal solutions to accommodate high-capacity channels, generated by conventional optical transmission systems, while enabling quantum-safe secure communications. When co-propagating classical channels with quantum channels at different wavelengths in the same optical medium adopting WDM, different impairments and suitable channel power and spacing should be considered. The use of alternative bands and the adoption of MCFs are effective solutions for addressing the coexistence and optimizing the performance of classical and quantum channels.

Additional aspects should be also taken into account, including the key management and control system, in particular when considering quantum networks, adopting trusted nodes, or approaches beyond point-to-point systems. SDN can facilitate the integration of QKD with conventional systems and the key management in optical networks, enabling quantum secure communications and advanced functionalities [14]. This results especially relevant in a disaggregated environment and towards an integration in the network infrastructure.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A suitable combination of photonic technologies and advanced/programmable features addresses the demand for Tb/s capacities and dynamic adaptation, as critical needs of future networks. Multi-band transmission allows to increase the optical bandwidth by a factor of 10, compared to conventional C-band system, enabling to reach high-capacity targets. SDM enables further capacity scaling according to a factor depending to the number of adopted fibers/cores. Capacities of up to 1.6Tb/s over a metro network multi-hop path have been demonstrated adopting our programmable S-BVT design. Spectral and spatial channels should coexist with quantum channels for the network evolution towards integrating quantum communication technologies and enabling quantum secure networks. Multi-band and SDM can facilitate the coexistence of classical and quantum channels. Suitable CV-QKD protocols and SDN ease the envisioned integration in the network infrastructure.

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